

Romanian Orthodox Church

By Giuseppe Tateo, New Europe College Bucharest

Entry tags: Religious Group, Orthodoxy

The Romanian Orthodox Church (henceforth ROC) is an Eastern Christian denomination. It represents the largest religious group in Romania (86.45% in 2011). Although the first evidence of Christianization of modern-day Romanian territories (Lower Moesia) dates back to the 3rd century, this entry's time span runs from the achievement of the status of autocephalous Metropolis of Romania in 1885 – following the creation of the Kingdom of Romania in 1881 – up to the present day. The Metropolis of Romania was eventually raised to the rank of Patriarchate (its current jurisdiction) in 1925. The ROC is structured in Romania (thus excluding its dioceses abroad) into twenty-nine dioceses, fourteen of which have been established since 1990 (seven have been just re-opened after the communist leadership had disbanded them and another seven have been newly established). The Patriarch is the head and representative of the Romanian Orthodox Church, but decision making is the prerogative of the Holy Synod, which meets twice per year. The Holy Synod, which is the highest authority of the ROC, is formed by six Metropolitanates, sixteen Archbishoprics and thirteen Bishoprics with jurisdiction in Romania, plus some representatives for Romanian Orthodox communities abroad, including the Republic of Moldova. On a local scale, Bishoprics and Archbishoprics are divided in Protopopiates and, eventually, in parishes, which are the smallest units (Tateo 2020: 62). The theological framework organizing the orthodoxy and the orthopraxis of the ROC is the same of the other eight Eastern Orthodox churches, which are all autocephalous but in full communion with one another. The Romanian Orthodox faithful worship with particular devotion Saint Nicholas, Saint Parascheva, Saint Filofteia, Saint Andrew, Saint George, Saints Constantin and Elena, and Saint Dimitrie. The Orthodox Easter is the most important feast day of the year, while weekly services revolve around the Sunday mass. Pilgrimage to monasteries is a crucial form of religious practice which gathers thousands of believers every year: the Saint Parascheva is the largest one and takes place at the Metropolitan Cathedral of Iași on October 14th. The most popular Orthodox monasteries in Romania are Putna, Moldovița, Sucevița, Voroneț, Prislop, Cernica, and Sihastria. Source: Tateo, G. 2020. *Under the Sign of the Cross. The People's Salvation Cathedral and the Church-Building Industry in Postsocialist Romania*. London/New York: Berghahn Books.

Date Range: 1885 CE - 2020 CE

Region: România

Region tags: Europe, Southeastern Europe

Romanian Orthodox in Romania

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Păcurariu, Mircea (2007). *Romanian Christianity*. In: Parry, Ken (2007); *The Blackwell Companion to Eastern Christianity*; Blackwell Publishing;
- Source 2: Stan, Lavinia; Turcescu, Lucian (2007). *Religion and Politics in Post-Communist Romania*. Oxford University Press.

– Source 3: Madgearu, Alexandru (2004). "The Spreading of Christianity in the rural areas of post-Roman Dacia (4th–7th centuries)" in *Archaeus* (2004), VIII, pp. 41–59.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Romanian-Orthodox-Church>

Specific to this answer:

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Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: https://patriarhia.ro/images/documente/statutul_bor.pdf

General Variables

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are they written:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are they oral:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

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Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

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Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious

community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

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↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

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↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

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Notes: When they are ordained, priests become a medium of divine grace (har) and are supposed to perform pastoral activities among the faithful. Both high (bishops and archbishops, who are monks) and low clergy (priests, deacons) are trained in transmitting the scriptures.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: After the death of the communist party secretary Gheorghiu-Dej in 1965, the new regime ushered in by Ceaușescu was marked by an autarchic drift, whose main ideological tool

consisted in brushing up on the nationalist discourse. The promotion of a nationalist ideology after the mid-1960s facilitated the collaboration between communist leaders and religious representatives; the outcomes of this process was the reinforcement of nationalist sentiments that lead to postsocialist inter-denominational and inter-ethnic disputes.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: Quarrels and tensions over property restitution have been reported throughout the 1990s and the 2000s between Orthodox and Greek-Catholics. This has led to occasional beatings and fights, but not to serious episodes of violence (i.e. killings). Also, Islamophobic protests have taken place in Bucharest in 2016 to prevent the construction of a mosque, but no episode of violence against Muslims has been reported.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 13000

Notes: The largest religious monument is the "People's Salvation Cathedral", which is still under construction. It is the highest Orthodox cathedral in the world, located in the centre of Bucharest, on one of the city's highest point (Arsenal Hill), perceptible not just visually but also aurally thanks to the 15km range of its bells, and located only a few hundred metres away from the Parliament, the Ministry of Defence and the Romanian Academy of Sciences.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 120

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Height, square meters: 500

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 20

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 16307004

Notes: This estimation dates back to the 2011 census in Romania. To the present day, about 4 million Orthodox Romanians live outside Romania.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– No

Notes: The answer is yes only for those who convert to Orthodoxy. Otherwise, members are affiliated through baptism when they are infants.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Baptism

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Notes: Beyond the new national cathedral, several cross-shaped monuments have been built in Bucharest and Timisoara. Newly-built religious infrastructure includes also other thirty cathedrals all over the country.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Temples:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Altars:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Cross-shaped monuments

Notes: Cross-shaped monuments have multiplied across the country and in the capital since 1990, promoted by state authorities (the Romanian Intelligence Service and the Ministry of Culture), civil associations as well as by religious institutions. Not just intended to commemorate the dead, their usage is often political, as they are tools to take distance from the socialist past and place oneself on the right side of history.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 86

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: After the end of socialism the Greek Catholic Church has been re-opened, while Neoprotestant churches have been growing fast (especially Pentecostals and Adventists). Although the Romanian Orthodox Church still represents the overwhelming majority of the religious population, church leaders consider the growing secularization of young urbanites and the success of neoprotestantism as potential threats.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Yes

Notes: The State Secretariat for Religious Affairs (SSRA) purveys economical support for the remuneration of clerical personnel. The sums allocated to pay salaries grow yearly in accordance with the rise of the minimum wage. Law 153/2017 stipulates that the SSRA provide full salaries for 1,385 positions composing the higher management personnel of all religious denominations, while it also covers between 65 and 80% of the wages for the lower clergy (15,272 positions), whose salaries are matched against those of pre-university state education teaching staff.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

Notes: The expansion of the church-building sector is a direct consequence of the substantial economic support offered by public institutions. The governmental funds channeled by the SSRA to the eighteen religious groups (whose the ROC is the largest) have been growing year after year, marking a new record in 2018 after a foreseeable decline due to the economic crisis

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

Notes: Article 29 of the Constitution affirms that religions shall be autonomous from the state but shall enjoy support from it.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

Notes: However, high-clergy representatives such as the Patriarch, archbishops and bishops are considered administrative positions and their salaries are adjusted to those of political officials.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– At home

– Some public spaces

Notes: And, obviously, in houses of worship too.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Eyes (stylized or not):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Notes: The role of icons is particularly important in Orthodoxy. The theology of the icon is a theological tradition rooted in the Russian neo-hesychast movement between the end of the nineteenth and first half of the twentieth century. The main figures of this theological turn were Paul Evdokimov, Pavel Florensky and Vladimir Lossky, whose works have been translated into Romanian and are today classic reading for priests, icon painters, restorers and even fine arts students. A classic reading in this domain is Lossky, Vladimir and Leonid Ouspensky. [1952] 1999. *The Meaning of Icons*. Crestwood, NY: St. Vladimir's Seminary Press.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: Orthodox churches are always oriented towards east and possibly built on a hilly ground.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: Pilgrimage to monasteries is a crucial form of religious practice which gathers thousands of believers every year: the Saint Parascheva is the largest one and takes place at the Metropolitan Cathedral of Iași on October 14th. The most popular Orthodox monasteries in Romania are Putna, Moldovița, Sucevița, Voroneț, Prislop, Cernica, and Sihastria. Far from being exclusively a manifestation of faith on behalf of the pilgrims, such events are often the single occasion for many Romanians (especially women) to travel and flee a routine of hard work. Therefore, the atmosphere is often festive.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (common)

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: After the death of the communist party secretary Gheorghiu-Dej in 1965, the new regime ushered in by Ceaușescu was marked by an autarchic drift, whose main ideological tool consisted in brushing up on the nationalist discourse. The promotion of a nationalist ideology after the mid-1960s facilitated the collaboration between communist leaders and religious representatives; the outcomes of this process was the reinforcement of nationalist sentiments that lead to postsocialist inter-denominational and inter-ethnic disputes.

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Notes: Quarrels and tensions over property restitution have been reported throughout the 1990s and the 2000s between Orthodox and Greek-Catholics. This has led to occasional beatings and fights, but not to serious episodes of violence (i.e. killings). Also, Islamophobic protests have taken place in Bucharest in 2016 to prevent the construction of a mosque, but no episode of violence against Muslims has been reported.

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Notes: The answer is yes only for those who convert to Orthodoxy. Otherwise, members are affiliated through baptism when they are infants.

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Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

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Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Assigned by gender:

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Notes: Baptism

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Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 16307004

Notes: This estimation dates back to the 2011 census in Romania. To the present day, about 4 million Orthodox Romanians live outside Romania.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

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– Yes

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Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

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Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

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– Square meters: 13000

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Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 120

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Height, square meters: 500

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 20

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Notes: Beyond the new national cathedral, several cross-shaped monuments have been built in

Bucharest and Timisoara. Newly-built religious infrastructure includes also other thirty cathedrals all over the country.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Temples:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Altars:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Cross-shaped monuments

Notes: Cross-shaped monuments have multiplied across the country and in the capital since 1990, promoted by state authorities (the Romanian Intelligence Service and the Ministry of Culture), civil associations as well as by religious institutions. Not just intended to commemorate the dead, their usage is often political, as they are tools to take distance from the socialist past and place oneself on the right side of history.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– At home

– Some public spaces

Notes: And, obviously, in houses of worship too.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Notes: The role of icons is particularly important in Orthodoxy. The theology of the icon is a theological tradition rooted in the Russian neo-hesychast movement between the end of the nineteenth and first half of the twentieth century. The main figures of this theological turn were Paul Evdokimov, Pavel Florensky and Vladimir Lossky, whose works have been translated into Romanian and are today classic reading for priests, icon painters, restorers and even fine arts students. A classic reading in this domain is

Lossky, Vladimir and Leonid Ouspensky. [1952] 1999. *The Meaning of Icons*. Crestwood, NY: St. Vladimir's Seminary Press.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: Orthodox churches are always oriented towards east and possibly built on a hilly ground.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: Pilgrimage to monasteries is a crucial form of religious practice which gathers thousands of believers every year: the Saint Parascheva is the largest one and takes place at the Metropolitan Cathedral of Iași on October 14th. The most popular Orthodox monasteries in Romania are Putna, Moldovița, Sucevița, Voroneț, Prislop, Cernica, and Sihastria. Far from being exclusively a manifestation of faith on behalf of the pilgrims, such events are often the single occasion for many Romanians (especially women) to travel and flee a routine of hard work. Therefore, the atmosphere is often festive.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (common)

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Food:

– Yes

Notes: Fasting is one of the ways believers can discipline their lives and thus get closer to God (entheosis), which is the ultimate goal of religious practice. There are different kinds of fasting: absolute (no food or drinks whatsoever); dry (only one meal per day; only food, water, fruit and vegetables are admitted); simple (only boiled food, no oil admitted). In all such cases the consumption of food of animal origin is not allowed (except for fish). There are four main fasting periods throughout the calendar year: on Lent (the most important fasting), Nativity, Assumption of Mary and around St. Peter and Paul's day.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Blasphemy is also taboo.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Incest:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: Homosexual intercourse is still widely discouraged by many Romanian Orthodox and is understood as a serious sin. Oral sex is also considered a sin by ordained priests and zealots.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Notes: (From the old testament, Exodus 20:2-17 and Deutoronomy 5:6-17) Fifth commandment: "Honour thy father and thy mother"

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Notes: (From the old testament, Exodus 20:2-17 and Deutoronomy 5:6-17) Seventh commandment: "Thou shalt not steal"

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: The 2008 European Values Survey showed that church attendance in Romania is not that high, the first places being occupied by Catholic countries like Poland, Italy and Ireland. In Orthodoxy, to attend the main feasts of the liturgical year, to fast before Easter and take part in pilgrimages is deemed more important than regular church attendance, if the latter hides a feeling of constriction and duty rather than a sincere wish to go to church. An Orthodox believer is often told not to feel bound to go to church just because – being part of the religious community – she is expected to do so: 'We should not feel like slaves!' (Să nu ne simțim slugii!), a priest I met in Bucharest during fieldwork used to repeat – quoting Saint Neagoe Basarab – during a weekly meeting organized for university students.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: (From the old testament, Exodus 20:2-17 and Deutoronomy 5:6-17) Third commandment: "Remember the sabbath day, to keep it holy"

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Notes: While some contemporary Orthodox theologians (like the Greek Orthodox Christos Yannaras) justify the hesitant involvement of Orthodox churches in fighting inequality or social and economic exclusion, thus preparing the groundwork for the unfortunate encounter of neoliberalism and Orthodoxy, other observers like Alexandru Racu (2017) illustrates that an Orthodox social theology does exist and could even be a valid alternative to the 'antisocial' (as his book title suggests) paradigm fostered by well-known contemporary Orthodox intellectuals (from Horia-Roman Patapievi to Teodor Baconsi and Mihai Neamțu). Racu's argument is supported by a rich, heterogeneous reference literature that comprises church fathers (St Basil

the Great, St John Chrysostom), Orthodox theologians like the Russian Serghei Bulgakov or the Greek Georgios Mantzaridis, and the official position of Russian Orthodox Church on social doctrine. Sources: Tateo 2020: 108; Racu 2017.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– No

Notes: The old testament is rife with reference to personal care, as the "body is a temple of the Holy Spirit within you" (1 Corinthians 6:19). However, contemporary religious practice is little concerned with rules over personal hygiene.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Witnessing faith and avoiding "heresy"

Notes: Let me quote a popular parable from the 'Sayings of the Desert Fathers' (Patericul Egiptean), a collection of sayings and tales about early Christian hermits, ascetics and monks who lived in the desert of Egypt. It goes like this: 'It was said concerning Abba Agathon that some monks came to find him having heard tell of his great discernment. Wanting to see if he would lose his temper they said to him "Aren't you that Agathon who is said to be a fornicator and a proud man?" "Yes, it is very true", he answered. They resumed, "Aren't you that Agathon who is always talking nonsense?" "I am". Again they said "Aren't you Agathon the heretic?" But at that he replied "I am not a heretic". So they asked him, "Tell us why you accepted everything we cast you, but repudiated this last insult". He replied "The first accusations I take to myself, for that is good for my soul. But heresy is separation from God. Now I have no wish to be separated from God". At this saying they were astonished at his discernment and returned, edified' (Aa.Vv. 1984: 20-21).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: At the same time, in the Orthodox world it is not hard to find theologians, monks or ordinary priests discouraging the faithful from adopting a moralizing attitude. Dumitru Staniloae, the most renowned Romanian Orthodox theologian of the twentieth century, claimed that 'right when the moralizing element prevails in religion, we get closer to sectarians' (Ciachir 2013: 79), his term for Protestants. Similarly, hieromonk Rafail Noica considered that 'the lowest step of faith is morality' (Ciachir 2014: 92), while Christos Yannaras warned that 'ethics taints the Church, . . . it is the most apparent form of secularisation of the Church' (Yannaras 2004: 129-30). To suspend moral judgements and escape legalistic interpretations of religious life is a peculiarity on which Orthodox spiritual leaders often dwell and which marks a clear difference from Western Christianity. (Tateo 2020: 135-136). Sources: Ciachir, Dan. 2013. *Starea bisericii*. Cluj-Napoca: Editura Mega; Yannaras, Christos. 2004. *Libertatea moralei*. Bucharest: Fundația Anastasia; Tateo, Giuseppe. 2020. *Under the sign of the cross: the people's salvation cathedral and the church-building industry in postsocialist Romania*. New York: Berghahn Books.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: The messiah is Jesus Christ and his return on earth is supposed to redeem humankind.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Notes: Interestingly enough, kinship relations are imagined between the forefathers of

the Romanian nation and the kings who run the Kingdom of Romania between 1881 and 1947. The close relationship between nationalism and kinship was already explored in the Romanian context by Verdery, who suggested bringing 'national identities into the larger category of social relations within which (...)they belong: kinship. (...) Nationalism is thus a kind of ancestor worship, a system of patrilineal kinship in which national heroes occupy the place of clan elders in defining a nation as a noble lineage' (Verdery 1999: 41). In his speech to the Holy Synod in 1920, King Ferdinand offered a perfect example of what Verdery meant: while explaining the reasons for constructing the national cathedral, he took inspiration from 'our good ancestors: Stephen the Great, Michael the Brave, Matei Basarab, up to King Charles I'. Foreign kings like Charles and Ferdinand Hohenzollern - whose family hailed from modern-day Baden-Württemberg - became part of the patrilineal lineage that constitutes the Romanian ethnic nation. (Tateo 2020: 94).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

–Yes [specify]: God is holy, almighty and omnipresent. It is one but at the same time it is manifested in three persons: the father, the son, and the holy spirit. Common attributes associated to God are joy, wisdom, truth, power, holiness, and purity.

Notes: Further readings on the topic: Ware, Timothy. 1963. *The Orthodox Church*. Harmondsworth, Middlesex: Penguin Books; *The Divine Liturgy of St. John Chrysostom* (Gideon House Books, 2015).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of

human affairs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: God is considered omniscient and has knowledge of everything.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Notes: Prayers can establish different forms of interaction with the sacred. Stahl and Venbrux (2011: 150) distinguish between five kinds of prayer among Orthodox Romanians: adoration, confession, petition, praise and thanksgiving. The petition kind of prayer is intended to ask for help, health or to solve any kind of problem the faithful may have. Praise and thanksgiving are meant, instead, to express gratitude to God for his rewards. For an ethnographic description of contemporary Romanian Orthodox lived religion, see Stahl, Irina and Erik Venbrux. 2011. 'Ritual Multiplication: On Lived Religion in Bucharest', *Jaarboek voor liturgieonderzoek* 27(1): 139-67.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: For instance, the holy scriptures - and especially the old testament - present God as manifesting sentiments of anger or committing punitive actions. This is even more evident in the way Jesus is depicted in the Gospel - that is - as a person who suffers, expresses disappointment etc.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ In trance possession:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: When they are ordained, priests become a medium of divine grace. They supposedly do not lose this quality even if defrocked. Monks and priests are supposed to be vehicles of divine grace and this transmission of grace happens not only by means of their bodies, but also via the words they use and the mild attitude they adopt.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: The faithful can read events happening in everyday life as signs that manifest the will of god and the unraveling of a divine plan. One example is the concept of providence, which is widespread among Christians and is not limited to Orthodox.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: 'Previously human spirits' can comprehend the saints, the Virgin Mary, and all the dead. The interaction with the first two is of course different than dead commemoration. The faithful ask for protection or forgiveness to the saints or to the Virgin Mary and they often have a special attachment to a specific saint. The prayer for the dead, instead, is meant to protect them in the afterlife.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Apparitions of the virgin mary are venerated and the places where these have occurred have become popular pilgrimage sites (which are attended by believers of different denominations).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: Beyond the saints and the Virgin Mary, who can communicate with the faithful, the gift of foresight (harul clarviziunii) is said to be a feature of few charismatic priests as well.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits can reward:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits can punish:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Saints operate by asking God to fulfill the faithful's requests. To this extent, their

action is indirect.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ In trance possession:

– No

Notes: Again it is important to distinguish between theology and folk religion. Theologically speaking, previously human spirits do not communicate through trance possession. Humans can be possessed by evil, but this happens under the influence of demons, that is, fallen angels (which cannot be considered "previously human spirits"). However, in rural Romania it has been reported about people that had been possessed by the spirits of the dead who did not receive proper burial (see Michael Bird and Ovidiu Dunel-Stancu, 2017. "I dug out his heart with a pitchfork", 18 December, Theblacksea.eu, https://theblacksea.eu/_old/mirror/theblacksea.eu/stories/article/en/exorcism-romanian-style.html)

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Through divination processes:

– No

Notes: However, due to the ascetic life they lead, some charismatic monks are deemed to have powers such as clairvoyance or the ability to perform miraculous healings. It can be considered a form of divination to consult a spiritual father considered capable of clairvoyance. Such monks are very popular and attract dozens of faithful on a daily basis. The reasons for meeting them revolve around an important decision to be taken. They could be related to health issues, sentimental relationships, family issues, and even more mundane affairs such as financial investments.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Only through specialists:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Angels and Demons do play an important role in the cosmology of Orthodox Romanians. The former are meant to protect the faithful, the latter to lead into temptation. Such being are anthropomorphic but cannot be considered human.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

Notes: The only being that can be considered human-divine is Jesus, who is human but at the same time has a divine nature.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Notes: God is on top the hierarchy, angels and saints are placed on a lower level.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present (but not emphasized)

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– Only specialized religious class

– Only one class of society

– Only one gender

– All individuals (any time period)

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Notes: Devotion to saints and the Virgin Mary can result in them interceding with God to reward the faithful.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness[]:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Cremation:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Mummification:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: Immurement is also practiced in cemeteries.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: Although they are not theologically sanctioned and discouraged by priests, folk religion practices such as leaving some money or personal belongings (a comb or a lipstick) in the hands of the dead are still present. Instead, it is common - and in line with the church protocol - to leave an icon on the chest of

the dead during the funeral, but this is removed before the burial and eventually left on the tomb.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: Suggested readings on the topic: Verdery, Katherine. 1999. *The Political Lives of Dead Bodies*. New York: Columbia University Press. Rotar, Marius. 2013. *History of Modern Cremation in Romania*. Cambridge: Cambridge Scholars Publishing.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

As cenotaphs:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

In cemetery:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

Notes: The overwhelming majority of dead bodies among Orthodox Romanians are buried in cemeteries. However, it happens that in those villages with a too small cemetery, bodies are buried in the yard adjacent to the house.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Other formal burial type:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

Notes: "Eschatology permeates the entire life of the Church: Its services, sacraments and rites, its theological and moral doctrine, its asceticism and mysticism. The entire history of the Church is filled with eschatological expectations, beginning with the Resurrection and Ascension of Christ and continuing until the present day. Indeed, it is because the Resurrection has taken place - because we live in the time of the Resurrection - that eschatology is so fundamental to the Church." Alfeyev, Hilarion. 2008. "Eschatology" in Cunningham, Mary and Theokritoff, Mary B., *The Cambridge Companion to Orthodox Christian Theology*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 107-120.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Eschaton in this lifetime:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Eschaton at some other time:

– Yes [specify]: Eschaton is at unspecified time in future - it is impossible to say whether near or distant.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Restoration of the world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– No

Notes: Politics and religion are concepts made up by man. In the afterlife there is no establishment of a given political or religious system but of the Kingdom of God.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– No

Notes: The eschaton ends the life experience in this world. In this sense, no one survives it. The entire history of Christianity unfolds in the period of time between the first and second comings of the Saviour. With the establishment of the Kingdom of God and the divine judgement, the dead will resurrect and the body and soul of every individual will reunite.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: It is worth noting that the role of priests is not necessarily that of role models, but rather of ritual specialists who can offer spiritual and emotional help to the believers. A famous Romanian saying goes: 'do what the priest says, not what the priest does!' (fa ce zice popa, nu ce face popa!), which indicates that priests are not to be intended as role models, their importance lying, more generally, in their pastoral and liturgical activity.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Courage (in battle):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Courage (generic):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Strength (physical):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that

some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Cremation:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Mummification:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: Immurement is also practiced in cemeteries.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: Although they are not theologically sanctioned and discouraged by priests, folk religion practices such as leaving some money or personal belongings (a comb or a lipstick) in the hands of the dead are still present. Instead, it is common - and in line with the church protocol - to leave an icon on the chest of the dead during the funeral, but this is removed before the burial and eventually left on the tomb.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: Suggested readings on the topic: Verdery, Katherine. 1999. *The Political Lives of Dead Bodies*. New York: Columbia University Press. Rotar, Marius. 2013. *History of Modern Cremation in Romania*. Cambridge: Cambridge Scholars Publishing.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ As cenotaphs:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

Notes: The overwhelming majority of dead bodies among Orthodox Romanians are buried in cemeteries. However, it happens that in those villages with a too small cemetery, bodies are buried in the yard adjacent to the house.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Notes: Interestingly enough, kinship relations are imagined between the forefathers of the Romanian nation and the kings who run the Kingdom of Romania between 1881 and 1947. The close relationship between nationalism and kinship was already explored in the Romanian context by Verdery, who suggested bringing 'national identities into the larger category of social relations within which (...)they belong: kinship. (...) Nationalism is thus a kind of ancestor worship, a system of patrilineal kinship in which national heroes occupy the place of clan elders in defining a nation as a noble lineage' (Verdery 1999: 41). In his speech to the Holy Synod in 1920, King Ferdinand offered a perfect example of what Verdery meant: while explaining the reasons for constructing the national cathedral, he took inspiration from 'our good ancestors: Stephen the Great, Michael the Brave, Matei Basarab, up to King Charles I'. Foreign kings like Charles and Ferdinand Hohenzollern - whose family hailed from modern-day Baden-Württemberg - became part of the patrilineal lineage that constitutes the Romanian ethnic nation. (Tateo 2020: 94).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: God is holy, almighty and omnipresent. It is one but at the same time it is manifested in three persons: the father, the son, and the holy spirit. Common attributes associated to God are joy, wisdom, truth, power, holiness, and purity.

Notes: Further readings on the topic: Ware, Timothy. 1963. *The Orthodox Church*. Harmondsworth, Middlesex: Penguin Books; *The Divine Liturgy of St. John Chrysostom* (Gideon House Books, 2015).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
– Yes [specify]: God is considered omniscient and has knowledge of everything.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god can reward:
– Yes

Notes: Prayers can establish different forms of interaction with the sacred. Stahl and Venbrux (2011: 150) distinguish between five kinds of prayer among Orthodox Romanians: adoration, confession, petition, praise and thanksgiving. The petitional kind of prayer is intended to ask for help, health or to solve any kind of problem the faithful may have. Praise and thanksgiving are meant, instead, to express gratitude to God for his rewards. For an ethnographic description of contemporary Romanian Orthodox lived religion, see Stahl, Irina and Erik Venbrux. 2011. 'Ritual Multiplication: On Lived Religion in Bucharest', *Jaarboek voor liturgieonderzoek* 27(1): 139-67.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: For instance, the holy scriptures - and especially the old testament - present God as manifesting sentiments of anger or committing punitive actions. This is even more evident in the way Jesus is depicted in the Gospel - that is - as a person who suffers, expresses disappointment etc.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ In trance possession:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: When they are ordained, priests become a medium of divine grace. They supposedly do not lose this quality even if defrocked. Monks and priests are supposed to be vehicles of divine grace and this transmission of grace happens not only by means of their bodies, but also via the words they use and the mild attitude they adopt.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: The faithful can read events happening in everyday life as signs that manifest the will of god and the unraveling of a divine plan. One example is the concept of providence, which is widespread among Christians and is not limited to Orthodox.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: 'Previously human spirits' can comprehend the saints, the Virgin Mary, and all the dead. The interaction with the first two is of course different than dead commemoration. The faithful ask for protection or forgiveness to the saints or to the Virgin Mary and they often have a special attachment to a specific saint. The prayer for the dead, instead, is meant to protect them in the afterlife.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Apparitions of the virgin mary are venerated and the places where these have occurred have become popular pilgrimage sites (which are attended by believers of different denominations).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: Beyond the saints and the Virgin Mary, who can communicate with the faithful, the gift of foresight (*harul clarviziunii*) is said to be a feature of few charismatic priests as well.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits can reward:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits can punish:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Saints operate by asking God to fulfill the faithful's requests. To this extent, their action is indirect.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ In trance possession:

– No

Notes: Again it is important to distinguish between theology and folk religion. Theologically speaking, previously human spirits do not communicate through trance possession. Humans can be possessed by evil, but this happens under the influence of demons, that is, fallen angels (which cannot be considered "previously human spirits"). However, in rural Romania it has been reported about people that had been possessed by the spirits of the dead who did not receive proper burial (see Michael Bird and Ovidiu Dunel-Stancu, 2017. "I dug out his heart with a pitchfork", 18 December, Theblacksea.eu, https://theblacksea.eu/_old/mirror/theblacksea.eu/stories/article/en/exorcism-romanian-style.html)

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Through divination processes:

– No

Notes: However, due to the ascetic life they lead, some charismatic monks are deemed to have powers such as clairvoyance or the ability to perform miraculous healings. It can be considered a form of divination to consult a spiritual father considered capable of clairvoyance. Such monks are very popular and attract dozens of faithful on a daily basis. The reasons for meeting them revolve around an important decision to be taken. They could be related to health issues, sentimental relationships, family issues, and even more mundane affairs such as financial investments.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Only through specialists:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Angels and Demons do play an important role in the cosmology of Orthodox Romanians. The former are meant to protect the faithful, the latter to lead into temptation. Such being are anthropomorphic but cannot be considered human.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

Notes: The only being that can be considered human-divine is Jesus, who is human but at the same time has a divine nature.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Notes: God is on top the hierarchy, angels and saints are placed on a lower level.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Food:

– Yes

Notes: Fasting is one of the ways believers can discipline their lives and thus get closer to God (entheosis), which is the ultimate goal of religious practice. There are different kinds of fasting: absolute (no food or drinks whatsoever); dry (only one meal per day; only food, water, fruit and vegetables are admitted); simple (only boiled food, no oil admitted). In all such cases the consumption of food of animal origin is not allowed (except for fish). There are four main fasting periods throughout the calendar year: on Lent (the most important fasting), Nativity, Assumption of Mary and around St. Peter and Paul's day.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Blasphemy is also taboo.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Incest:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: Homosexual intercourse is still widely discouraged by many Romanian Orthodox and is understood as a serious sin. Oral sex is also considered a sin by ordained priests and zealots.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Notes: (From the old testament, Exodus 20:2-17 and Deuteronomy 5:6-17) Fifth commandment: "Honour thy father and thy mother"

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Notes: (From the old testament, Exodus 20:2-17 and Deuteronomy 5:6-17) Seventh commandment: "Thou shalt not steal"

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: The 2008 European Values Survey showed that church attendance in Romania is not that high, the first places being occupied by Catholic countries like Poland, Italy and Ireland. In Orthodoxy, to attend the main feasts of the liturgical year, to fast before Easter and take part in pilgrimages is deemed more important than regular church attendance, if the latter hides a feeling of constriction and duty rather than a sincere wish to go to church. An Orthodox believer is often told not to feel bound to go to church just because – being part of the religious community – she is expected to do so: ‘We should not feel like slaves!’ (Să nu ne simțim slugii!), a priest I met in Bucharest during fieldwork used to repeat – quoting Saint Neagoe Basarab – during a weekly meeting organized for university students.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: (From the old testament, Exodus 20:2-17 and Deuteronomy 5:6-17) Third commandment: "Remember the sabbath day, to keep it holy"

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Notes: While some contemporary Orthodox theologians (like the Greek Orthodox Christos Yannaras) justify the hesitant involvement of Orthodox churches in fighting inequality or social and economic exclusion, thus preparing the groundwork for the unfortunate encounter of neoliberalism and Orthodoxy, other observers like Alexandru Racu (2017) illustrates that an Orthodox social theology does exist and could even be a valid alternative to the ‘antisocial’ (as his book title suggests) paradigm fostered by well-known contemporary Orthodox intellectuals (from Horia-Roman Patapievi to Teodor Baconschi and Mihai Neamțu). Racu’s argument is supported by a rich, heterogeneous reference literature that comprises church fathers (St Basil the Great, St John Chrysostom), Orthodox theologians like the Russian Serghei Bulgakov or the Greek Georgios Mantzaridis, and the official position of Russian Orthodox Church on social doctrine. Sources: Tateo 2020: 108; Racu 2017.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– No

Notes: The old testament is rife with reference to personal care, as the "body is a temple of the Holy Spirit within you" (1 Corinthians 6:19). However, contemporary religious practice is little concerned with rules over personal hygiene.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Witnessing faith and avoiding "heresy"

Notes: Let me quote a popular parable from the 'Sayings of the Desert Fathers' (Patericul Egiptean), a collection of sayings and tales about early Christian hermits, ascetics and monks who lived in the desert of Egypt. It goes like this: 'It was said concerning Abba Agathon that some monks came to find him having heard tell of his great discernment. Wanting to see if he would lose his temper they said to him "Aren't you that Agathon who is said to be a fornicator and a proud man?" "Yes, it is very true", he answered. They resumed, "Aren't you that Agathon who is always talking nonsense?" "I am". Again they said "Aren't you Agathon the heretic?" But at that he replied "I am not a heretic". So they asked him, "Tell us why you accepted everything we cast you, but repudiated this last insult". He replied "The first accusations I take to myself, for that is good for my soul. But heresy is separation from God. Now I have no wish to be separated from God". At this saying they were astonished at his discernment and returned, edified' (Aa.Vv. 1984: 20-21).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Notes: Devotion to saints and the Virgin Mary can result in them interceding with God to reward the faithful.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: The messiah is Jesus Christ and his return on earth is supposed to redeem humankind.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

Notes: "Eschatology permeates the entire life of the Church: Its services, sacraments and rites, its theological and moral doctrine, its asceticism and mysticism. The entire history of the Church is filled with eschatological expectations, beginning with the Resurrection and Ascension of Christ and continuing until the present day. Indeed, it is because the Resurrection has taken place - because we live in the time of the Resurrection - that eschatology is so fundamental to the Church." Alfeyev, Hilarion. 2008. "Eschatology" in Cunningham, Mary and Theokritoff, Mary B., *The Cambridge Companion to Orthodox Christian Theology*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 107-120.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– Yes [specify]: Eschaton is at unspecified time in future - it is impossible to say whether near or distant.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Restoration of the world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Establishment of a new religious system:

– No

Notes: Politics and religion are concepts made up by man. In the afterlife there is no establishment of a given political or religious system but of the Kingdom of God.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– No

Notes: The eschaton ends the life experience in this world. In this sense, no one survives it. The entire history of Christianity unfolds in the period of time between the first and second comings of the Saviour. With the establishment of the Kingdom of God and the divine judgement, the dead will resurrect and the body and soul of every individual will reunite.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: At the same time, in the Orthodox world it is not hard to find theologians, monks or ordinary priests discouraging the faithful from adopting a moralizing attitude. Dumitru Staniloae, the most renowned Romanian Orthodox theologian of the twentieth century, claimed that 'right when the moralizing element prevails in religion, we get closer to sectarians' (Ciachir 2013: 79), his term for Protestants. Similarly, hieromonk Rafail Noica considered that 'the lowest step of faith is morality' (Ciachir 2014: 92), while Christos Yannaras warned that 'ethics taints the Church, . . . it is the most apparent form of secularisation of the Church' (Yannaras 2004: 129–30). To suspend moral judgements and escape legalistic interpretations of religious life is a peculiarity on which Orthodox spiritual leaders often dwell and which marks a clear difference from Western Christianity. (Tateo 2020: 135–136). Sources: Ciachir, Dan. 2013. *Starea bisericii*. Cluj-Napoca: Editura Mega; Yannaras, Christos. 2004. *Libertatea moralei*. Bucharest: Fundația Anastasia; Tateo, Giuseppe. 2020. *Under the sign of the cross: the people's salvation cathedral and the church-building industry in postsocialist Romania*. New York: Berghahn Books.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present (but not emphasized)

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Moral norms apply to:

- Only specialized religious class
- Only one class of society
- Only one gender
- All individuals (any time period)

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: It is worth noting that the role of priests is not necessarily that of role models, but rather of ritual specialists who can offer spiritual and emotional help to the believers. A famous Romanian saying goes: 'do what the priest says, not what the priest does!' (fa ce zice popa, nu ce face popa!), which indicates that priests are not to be intended as role models, their importance lying, more generally, in their pastoral and liturgical activity.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Courage (in battle):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Courage (generic):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Strength (physical):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Only ordained monks are supposed to be celibate. Priests and the lay are supposed to marry and start a family.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: From a strictly theological point of view, priests and all the faithful are subject to constraints on sexual activity, since humans, unlike animals, are not understood as sexual creatures and the role of sex is strictly bound to reproduction. In practice, partial sexual abstinence is adopted only by few zealot believers. If the faithful feels of having committed a sexual sin, he or she will confess with a priest or with his or her spiritual father (a spiritual father is an ordained priest or monk who follows closely the believer in his spiritual path)-

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Notes: Accepting ethical precepts makes the difference between good and bad believers, but membership in the Church community is granted simply upon baptism.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Notes: Some rites of passage entail only symbolically the marginalization and reacquisition in society of the new members.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: Baptism

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

–Hours: 1

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– No

Notes: However, even non-practising believers won't miss the two major events of the year: the Easter and Christmas mass

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Notes: During baptisms and weddings godfathers and godmothers (naşi) play an important ritual role and are supposed to watch over those who undertake the ritual.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Only ordained monks are supposed to be celibate. Priests and the lay are supposed to marry and start a family.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: From a strictly theological point of view, priests and all the faithful are subject to constraints on sexual activity, since humans, unlike animals, are not understood as sexual creatures and the role of sex is strictly bound to reproduction. In practice, partial sexual abstinence is adopted only by few zealot believers. If the faithful feels of having committed a sexual sin, he or she will confess with a priest or with his or her spiritual father (a spiritual father is an ordained priest or monk who follows closely the believer in his spiritual path)-

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Notes: Accepting ethical precepts makes the difference between good and bad believers, but membership in the Church community is granted simply upon baptism.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Notes: Some rites of passage entail only symbolically the marginalization and reacquisition in society of the new members.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: **Baptism**

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Hours: 1

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– No

Notes: However, even non-practising believers won't miss the two major events of the year: the Easter and Christmas mass

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Notes: During baptisms and weddings godfathers and godmothers (naši) play an important ritual role and are supposed to watch over those who undertake the ritual.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Society and Institutions

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Notes: Soul kitchens and charity actions are scattered, not institutionalized.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: Religious education is provided through the weekly services within the church and through the religion class at school.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Pastoralism

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Notes: Only monasteries resort to such forms of food production, parishes don't.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: Since the 10th century, Old Church Slavonic has progressively become the language used for both administrative and liturgical purposes. Starting with the 17th century, Slavonic religious texts started to be replaced with texts in Romanian language. The first bible in Romanian was printed in 1688. Source: V. Costăchel, P. P. Panaitescu, A. Cazacu. (1957) *Viața feudală în Țara Românească și Moldova (secolele XIV–XVI)* ("Feudal life in the Romanian and Moldovan Land (14th–16th centuries)", București, Editura Științifică

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: It is interesting to notice how the close relationship between state authorities and the ROC have made religious and lay calendars to converge on some dates. In fact, in 1995 the Parliament voted a law establishing that national heroes must be commemorated on the same day of the Feast of the Ascension. To modify the calendar is rarely a neutral operation, as states have been using this tool for social engineering purposes or ideological agendas. Such practices have not stopped in present-day Romania, as shown by the decision to celebrate a religious feast and a uniquely national one on the very same day.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Fishing

– Pastoralism

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Romanian state

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Romanian state

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Notes: Care for the elderly and the infirm is sometimes provided. When this is the case, it is in the framework of a partnership with state authorities which provide financial support.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Romanian state

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Notes: Soul kitchens and charity actions are scattered, not institutionalized.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Romanian state

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Romanian state

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Notes: Care for the elderly and the infirm is sometimes provided. When this is the case, it is in the framework of a partnership with state authorities which provide financial support.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Romanian state

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: Religious education is provided through the weekly services within the church and through the religion class at school.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: Since the 10th century, Old Church Slavonic has progressively become the language used for both administrative and liturgical purposes. Starting with the 17th century, Slavonic religious texts started to be replaced with texts in Romanian language. The first bible in Romanian was printed in 1688. Source: V. Costăchel, P. P. Panaitescu, A. Cazacu. (1957) *Viața feudală în Țara Românească și Moldova (secolele XIV-XVI)* ("Feudal life in the Romanian and Moldovan Land (14th-16th centuries)", București, Editura Științifică

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: It is interesting to notice how the close relationship between state authorities and the ROC have made religious and lay calendars to converge on some dates. In fact, in 1995 the Parliament voted a law establishing that national heroes must be commemorated on the same day of the Feast of the Ascension. To modify the calendar is rarely a neutral operation, as states have been using this tool for social engineering purposes or ideological agendas. Such practices have not stopped in present-day Romania, as shown by the decision to celebrate a religious feast and a uniquely national one on the very same day.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Notes: Only monasteries resort to such forms of food production, parishes don't.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

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